

***Spilostethus furcula* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1850) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Lygaeidae) found in Libya**

Torsten van der Heyden

Immenweide 83, 22523 Hamburg, Germany.

E-mail: tmvdh@web.de ORCID iD: 0000-0003-4138-7160

ABSTRACT: A record of *Spilostethus furcula* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1850) from Libya is reported. Information on the known distribution of the species is summarized.

KEYWORDS: *Spilostethus furcula*, new record, distribution, Libya, Mediterranean Region.

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The lygaeid *Spilostethus furcula* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1850) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Lygaeidae) is considered an Afrotropical species and is distributed in Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia, Madagascar and South Africa as well as in Iran, Israel, Saudi Arabia and Yemen (Péricart, 1998, 2001; Aukema et al., 2013, Piednoir et al., 2019).

Now, *S. furcula* can be reported for Libya: On 06.04.2022, an adult specimen was found by Marwan Ahmeedah Bin Yazeed

near Sidi as Sa'ih in the district of Tripoli (Fig. 1). This record extends the distribution area of *S. furcula* in the Maghreb eastwards.

In Europe, the species has been reported from the following countries: Spain (Péricart, 1998, 2001), Portugal (Goula & Mata, 2011), France (Dioli et al., 2019; Piednoir et al., 2019), Greece (Piednoir et al., 2019; van der Heyden, 2019), Italy (Dioli et al., 2019; Piednoir et al., 2019) and Malta (van der Heyden, 2021).

Considering the reports of the last few years, *S. furcula* seems to be spreading in the Mediterranean Region.

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Figure 1. *Spilostethus furcula* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1850), near Sidi as Sa'ih, Tripoli district, Libya, 06.04.2022. (Photo: Marwan Ahmeedah Bin Yazeed).